

Investigating Graduation and Dropout Among Doctoral Students in Canada: A Duration Model Analysis

Keywords: doctoral study, graduation, dropout, duration model, field of study, Canada.

Mots clés: études doctorales, diplôme, abandon, modèle de durée, domaine d'études, Canada.

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Abstract

This paper analyses administrative data on students who entered doctoral programs in Canada between 2011 and 2016, providing new insights into doctoral completion and dropout patterns. Graduation rates within seven years vary significantly, with rates exceeding 60 percent in fields such as the physical sciences, life sciences, and engineering, yet falling below 30 percent in the humanities. We estimate a competing risks duration model that accounts for both graduation and dropout events, incorporating variables such as gender, age, immigration status, field of study, institution, marital status, and family composition. Our findings indicate that, while controlling for other factors, female students are significantly less likely to drop out than male students but also less likely to graduate. International students exhibit significantly higher completion rates compared to their domestic counterparts. Additionally, there are significant variations in the likelihood of graduation and dropout across different fields of study, ages, institutions, marital statuses, household arrangements, and the number of children.

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1 Introduction

The issue of extended completion times and high dropout rates at the doctoral level is a significant concern. In Canada, only about 50 percent of doctoral students who enrolled between 2011 and 2015 graduated after six years, as reported by [Statistics Canada \(2023a\)](#). Moreover, substantial differences exist across various fields of study. Completion rates within ten years ranged from approximately 70 percent in the life sciences to slightly over 40 percent in the humanities ([Canadian Association for Graduate Studies, 2003](#)). Given the considerable investments made by institutions and governments in doctoral education, the low completion rates and prolonged time-to-degree are concerning, not only within academia but also for policymakers and society at large.

Despite their significance, doctoral students remain an under-researched group in academic literature, primarily due to a lack of comprehensive data about them. Previous studies have explored factors associated with Ph.D. completion and dropout rates, such as gender, nationality, type of funding, field of study, and supervisor support. However, the majority of this literature relies on data from specific institutions or disciplines in the United States ([Abedi and Benkin, 1987](#); [Ehrenberg and Mavros, 1995](#); [Espenshade and Rodriguez, 1997](#); [Baker, 1998](#); [Siegfried and Stock, 2001](#); [Stock and Siegfried, 2006](#)), with some studies extending to European countries such as the United Kingdom ([Booth and Satchell, 1995](#)), Belgium ([Groenvynck, Vandeveldde and Van Rossem, 2013](#); [Wollast et al., 2018](#)), the Netherlands ([Van Ours and Ridder, 2003](#)), and Norway ([Mastekaasa, 2005](#)).

In Canada, research on doctoral students is relatively scarce. While some studies have addressed labour market outcomes using survey or census data ([Desjardins and King, 2011](#); [Maldonado, Wiggers and Arnold, 2013](#); [Edge and Munro, 2015](#); [Walters, Zarifa and Etmanski, 2021](#)), research specifically targeting the educational outcomes of doctoral students

remains limited, often due to issues with sample size. For example, [Seagram, Gould and Pyke \(1998\)](#) conduct a study at York University, surveying 154 doctoral graduates to investigate factors influencing their time to degree completion. Generalizing findings from students at specific universities or within certain disciplines to all doctoral students, or extrapolating these findings from one country to another, is problematic. Therefore, there is a pressing need for more comprehensive research to understand the educational outcomes of doctoral studies across Canada and the characteristics associated with these outcomes.

This paper addresses the gap in the literature by providing fresh insights into the completion and dropout of doctoral students, using large-scale administrative data that includes doctoral students in Canada since 2011. Using data from the Postsecondary Student Information System (PSIS) and the T1 Family Files (T1FF) tax records, we estimate a duration model by treating graduation and dropout—which includes both voluntary and required withdrawal—as competing risks in doctoral studies. In the model, we estimate graduation and dropout hazard functions, which represent the probability of these events occurring at a specific point in time, given that the student has not yet graduated or dropped out. By controlling for individual characteristics, we examine how these outcomes vary across different demographic groups. Factors considered include gender, age, cohort, immigration status, field of study, institution, marital status, and family composition. To further explore gender differences, we also estimate the model separately for men and women.

We find that female doctoral students are significantly less likely to drop out but also less likely to graduate compared to their male counterparts with similar characteristics. Specifically, the dropout hazard for female students is approximately ten percent lower, while their graduation hazard is about six percent lower. Compared to citizens, permanent residents are significantly more likely to drop out, whereas international students are more likely to graduate. Furthermore, obtaining permanent residency or citizenship is associated

with both a lower dropout hazard and a lower graduation hazard, indicating a longer study duration.

In terms of academic disciplines, the humanities report the lowest graduation hazards, while STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) and health-related fields exhibit higher completion hazards and lower dropout hazards. Moreover, later cohorts exhibit a reduced likelihood of graduation, a trend primarily driven by male students. Additionally, since 2019/2020—the onset of the COVID years—the dropout risk has increased by 16 percent, a change largely driven by female students.

Significant variations in dropout and graduation probabilities are also evident across age, institution, marital status, household arrangement (whether living with parents or not), and number of children. An interesting finding emerges regarding the association between having children and graduation outcomes by gender. For male students, having children appears to have little impact on graduation rates, with a significant reduction observed only when they have four or more children. In contrast, for female students, even having just one child is correlated with a significantly lower likelihood of graduating.

To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to analyse graduation and dropout patterns among doctoral students using large-scale administrative data in Canada. The findings could offer valuable quantitative insights into doctoral studies in Canada for students, policymakers, and university administrators.

The structure of this paper is as follows: Section 2 describes the data and sample and provides statistics on completion and dropout rates. Section 3 outlines our analytical model. Section 4 discusses the results of our estimation. Section 5 concludes.

2 Data

This paper uses data from the Education and Labour Market Longitudinal Platform (ELMLP) provided by Statistics Canada.¹ Our primary data source is the Postsecondary Student Information System (PSIS), which contains administrative records on student enrolment, level of study, fields of study, institution attended, degree completion, and basic demographic information, including immigration status, for students at Canadian public postsecondary institutions by reporting year.² The ELMLP includes the PSIS data from 2009/2010 to 2021/2022 for all provinces and territories. Because the PSIS provides annual information on the level of study and degree completion, we can track the enrolment of all doctoral students and determine whether they obtain a degree each year.³

The ELMLP also allows us to link the PSIS data to income and family records from the T1 Family File (T1FF). The T1FF is an annual administrative dataset of Canadian tax filers and their families. It includes selected information from income tax records from 1992 to 2020 for the PSIS population. We use additional information from the T1FF, such as students' marital status, whether they live with their parents, and the number of children they have, to complement our analysis.⁴

We define a cohort based on the start year of doctoral studies. While the PSIS provides the original program start date, Statistics Canada's technical reference guide for the ELMLP notes that this variable cannot reliably identify new entrants ([Statistics Canada, 2023b](#)). This is due to inconsistent reporting across provinces and territories, with some, like Quebec and Alberta, not reporting it at all, and others recording it inconsistently.

Following Statistics Canada's recommendation, we use the longitudinal aspect of the PSIS data to impute the start year of doctoral studies. New doctoral entrants are defined as those who enrolled in a specific year and had not been enrolled in a doctoral program for at least

the previous two years, tracing back to 2009. In other words, if a student’s first recorded year as a doctoral student is in or after 2011, we assume that this year marks the start of their doctoral studies. As noted in the same technical guide, looking two years back is generally sufficient to exclude nearly all earlier cohorts. Consequently, the earliest cohort in our study is the 2011 cohort—students who first appear in the PSIS as doctoral students in the 2011/2012 academic year. To make sure we have enough years of observations for each cohort, the latest cohort in our sample is those who entered doctoral study during 2016/2017. Since the PSIS covers up to 2021/2022 and the T1FF covers up to 2020, we can observe the 2011 cohort for up to 11 years in the PSIS and ten years in the T1FF. For the 2016 cohort, we can observe them for up to six years in the PSIS and five years in the T1FF. Table A1 in Appendix A reports the number of students by starting year and province, showing that the sample size in each province is stable over the years, which supports our imputation method.

We apply several additional sample restrictions. We include only those who started their doctoral studies between the ages of 21 and 55, which is when the majority of students begin their Ph.D. programs. We also exclude individuals for whom gender or immigration status is unknown, which represents a very small portion of the sample (about 0.05 percent). Additionally, we exclude those who graduated within two years, as this is very rare and constitutes less than one percent of the sample.⁵ We also exclude a few rare cases, such as students from certain universities with very small populations (fewer than 50 doctoral students). This includes those beginning their doctoral studies at St. Francis Xavier University, Mount St. Vincent University, and Nipissing University.

Our baseline sample consists of 61,750 students and 356,380 individual-year observations.⁶ For the majority of the sample, students are observed for consecutive years in the PSIS. However, approximately five percent of students have missing years in their PSIS records. Among these, about 70 percent have a one-year gap, while 15 percent have a two-year gap.

These gaps could be due to students taking a leave of absence. Unfortunately, there is no variable indicating whether a student is on leave. As a result, the duration studied reflects the elapsed time since enrolment, which may differ from the time the student is formally registered.

We also link the PSIS to the T1FF to obtain additional time-varying covariates on marital status and family composition.⁷ Not every individual-year observation in the PSIS can be linked to the T1FF, as not all individuals file taxes every year. For our linked sample, we impose the requirement that an individual must be linked to the T1FF for all available T1FF years. This means the person must have filed taxes consistently every year during the period under analysis.⁸ Our PSIS-T1FF linked sample includes 43,200 individuals and 235,000 individual-year observations, meaning that approximately 70 percent of doctoral students file taxes annually across all years.

Table 1 presents selected descriptive statistics for our baseline PSIS sample, with column (1) detailing the distribution by gender, immigration status, and field of study at the time of initial enrolment. In our baseline sample, 53 percent are male and 47 percent are female.⁹ The majority of the sample consists of Canadian citizens (51 percent), while permanent residents make up nine percent, and international students account for 40 percent.

The PSIS provides multiple variables for categorizing fields of study according to the Classification of Instructional Programs (CIP) Canada 2016 version, including a primary grouping code (CIPPG), a two-digit code, and a four-digit code. Due to limitations with CIPPG, such as the combined grouping of social sciences and law, we use these variables to create a new classification.¹⁰ Table B1 in Appendix B outlines our adjustments and re-groupings based on the PSIS codes for this new classification. Due to small sample sizes, we have excluded the categories of Personal, Protective, and Transportation Services, as well as the Unclassified category. As not all groupings have Ph.D. students, there are 13 major

Table 1: Selected Summary Statistics of the Baseline PSIS Sample

	(1) Fraction (%)	(2) Graduate within seven years (%)	(3) Graduation difference (%)	(4) Drop out within seven years (%)	(5) Dropout difference (%)
Gender					
Male	53.0	54.1	(base)	22.1	(base)
Female	47.0	48.5	-5.6***	21.3	-0.8*
Immigration Status					
International student	40.0	59.4	12.3***	19.0	-3.7***
Permanent resident	9.0	41.8	-5.3***	27.9	5.2***
Canadian citizen	51.0	47.1	(base)	22.7	(base)
Field of study					
Education	5.6	35.5	-5.4***	30.0	7.9***
Visual and Performing Arts	2.4	35.8	-5.1***	27.6	5.5***
Humanities	7.9	27.7	-13.2***	31.9	9.8***
Social and Behavioural Sciences	17.7	40.9	(base)	22.1	(base)
Business and Management	3.9	36.5	-4.4***	28.8	6.7***
Physical and Life Sciences	21.5	64.8	23.9***	16.3	-5.8***
Mathematics and Computer Sciences	6.0	54.3	13.4***	23.2	1.1
Agriculture	3.4	60.5	19.6***	19.1	-3.0**
Health	8.9	57.8	16.9***	19.2	-2.9***
Legal Studies	1.1	28.3	-12.6***	33.3	11.2***
Architecture	0.5	26.9	-14.0***	35.0	12.9***
Engineering	19.9	62.8	21.9***	18.7	-3.4***
Multidisciplinary Studies	1.1	38.5	-2.4	24.4	2.3
Total	100.0	51.5		21.7	

Notes: This table displays selected descriptive statistics for our baseline PSIS sample. Column (1) details the distribution of doctoral students by gender, immigration status, and field of study at the time of initial enrolment. As mandated by Statistics Canada, both the numerator and denominator of fractions are rounded to the nearest ten. Therefore, the sum of the fractions may not exactly equal 100 percent due to rounding. Columns (2) and (4) display the proportions of students who graduate and drop out within seven years for each category, respectively. Columns (3) and (5) show the differences in graduation and dropout rates relative to the reference group, along with significance levels determined using a proportion test. To ensure that we have graduation and dropout data for at least seven years, columns (2) and (3) use data from the 2011 to 2015 cohorts, while columns (4) and (5) are based on data from the 2011 to 2014 cohorts. *** significant at 1%; ** significant at 5%; * significant at 10%.

Source: Own calculation.

groupings in our sample. The largest group is in the physical and life sciences, representing 21.5 percent of students, while architecture has the lowest enrolment.

Column (2) of Table 1 reports the proportions of students who graduate within seven years for each category. Column (3) presents the differences in graduation rates relative to the reference group, along with an indicator of whether the difference is statistically significant determined by a proportion test. For these two columns, we analyse cohorts from 2011 to 2015, as these cohorts can be observed for at least seven years in the PSIS.

Columns (4) and (5) report the dropout rate within seven years and the differences in dropout rates, respectively. The PSIS dataset does not include a variable that directly indicates whether a student has dropped out. Instead, dropout status is inferred indirectly: if a student exits the dataset and does not return, they are classified as having dropped out by the end of their last observed year. That is, if a student's final recorded year in the dataset is not 2021, they are considered to have dropped out in that final year.¹¹ In the final year of the dataset (2021/2022), dropout status cannot be determined due to the lack of subsequent data. Dropout information is therefore available for six years for the 2015 cohort and five years for the 2016 cohort. Accordingly, columns (4) and (5) focus on cohorts from 2011 to 2014.

Men are significantly more likely than women to graduate within seven years—54.1 percent of men graduate compared to 48.5 percent of women. Women are slightly less likely to drop out than men, with this difference being significant at the ten percent level. Dropout can occur either voluntarily or due to being required to withdraw, each of which has different implications. However, the data does not provide information on the reasons for dropouts, which limits our ability to further explore this distinction.

International students are significantly more likely to graduate within seven years, with

approximately 60 percent graduating during this period. In comparison, permanent residents are significantly less likely to graduate than Canadian citizens, with only about 42 percent of permanent residents graduating within seven years, compared to 47 percent of Canadian citizens. Additionally, international students have significantly lower dropout rates, while permanent residents have significantly higher dropout rates compared to Canadian citizens.

Significant variations are observed in graduation and dropout rates across different fields of study. Physical and life sciences, along with engineering, exhibit the highest graduation rates within seven years, at 64.8 percent and 62.8 percent, respectively. These fields also report relatively low dropout rates, with physical and life sciences at 16.3 percent and engineering at 18.7 percent. Agriculture and health-related majors also demonstrate strong student success, characterized by high graduation rates and low dropout rates.

On the other hand, architecture reports the lowest graduation rate at only 26.9 percent and the highest dropout rate at 35.0 percent. Humanities and legal studies show notably low graduation rates, at 27.7 percent and 28.3 percent, respectively, coupled with high dropout rates—31.9 percent for humanities and 33.3 percent for legal studies. Generally, students in the natural sciences, applied sciences, and health sciences are more likely to graduate compared to those in education, the arts and humanities, social and behavioural sciences, and business.

Graduation and dropout rates within seven years across gender, immigration status, and field of study offer an initial insight into doctoral studies but cannot fully capture the nuances of time to degree and time to dropout, particularly when examining these student characteristics concurrently. Therefore, it is necessary to develop and estimate a model that leverages all available longitudinal data and includes relevant covariates to accurately identify the distinct impacts of each factor.

3 Model

In this section, we describe the model we use. Each year until the end of the observation period, students can be in one of the following states: dropout, graduate, or continue to enroll. Therefore, a duration model with competing risks is the appropriate model for estimation. Dropout and graduation are considered competing risks because only one of them can occur first. Given that we observe students' status annually, we use the discrete-time equivalent of the proportional hazards model (Cox, 1972; Prentice and Gloeckler, 1978; Meyer, 1990; DesJardins, Ahlburg and McCall, 1999; Willett and Singer, 2003).

Formally, time is represented discretely as $t = 1, 2, \dots, T$. For each risk $j \in \{1, 2\}$, the cause-specific hazard in $[t - 1, t)$ is the conditional probability that an individual will experience event j during the time period $[t - 1, t)$, given that no exit from any cause has occurred in any earlier time period. This is assumed to have the following functional form (conditional on individual characteristics):

$$h_j(t|\mathbf{x}) = 1 - \exp(-\exp(\mathbf{x}\boldsymbol{\beta}_j + \gamma_{jt})), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{x} is a vector of individual characteristics, and $\boldsymbol{\beta}_j$ and γ_{jt} are parameters to be estimated.

The cause-specific survivor function, which is the probability that an individual will not experience cause j up until time period t , is defined as:

$$S_j(t|\mathbf{x}) = \prod_{k=1}^t (1 - h_j(k|\mathbf{x})).$$

We assume that there is no dependence of the risks through unobserved heterogeneity, the

same as the assumption made by [Ehrenberg and Mavros \(1995\)](#). Therefore, for someone who survives up to period t , i.e., does not experience any event from any cause before the end of t , the joint survivor function is:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S(t|\mathbf{x}) &= S_1(t|\mathbf{x}) \times S_2(t|\mathbf{x}) \\
 &= \prod_{k=1}^t (1 - h_1(k|\mathbf{x})) \times \prod_{k=1}^t (1 - h_2(k|\mathbf{x})) \\
 &= \prod_{k=1}^t [(1 - h_1(k|\mathbf{x})) \times (1 - h_2(k|\mathbf{x}))].
 \end{aligned}$$

Before introducing the likelihood function, we now consider a few complications introduced by the nature of the doctoral study and by our data. The first is that there is usually a minimum period before a doctoral student can graduate. For example, doctoral students in economics typically have to take courses during the first two years, and it is impossible for them to complete their thesis and graduate within that time frame. In our data, it is very rare for students to obtain a doctoral degree within two years. As discussed in the previous data section, these cases are excluded from our sample. Therefore, same as [Booth and Satchell \(1995\)](#), we assume that students cannot graduate within the first two years, i.e., there is no completion risk within the first two years of enrolment.

Another issue arises from how we define dropout. As we discussed in the data section, dropout is inferred indirectly. In the final year covered by the data (i.e., 2021/2022), we cannot determine whether students have dropped out because we lack information for the subsequent year. Consequently, it is impossible to estimate dropout risks for that last year for each cohort.

Given these assumptions and constraints, we construct our likelihood function for estimation. Consider N individuals, indexed by $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$. We define a dummy variable d_i ,

which equals 1 if individual i drops out and 0 if individual i graduates by the end of our data period. Additionally, we define a second dummy variable c_i , which equals 1 if individual i is censored, meaning they are still enrolled at the end of our data period, and 0 otherwise. Clearly, if $c_i = 1$, d_i is unobserved. For each individual i , we observe $(t_i, d_i, c_i, \mathbf{x}_i)$, where t_i represents the duration of the individual's presence in the data (i.e., time-to-degree if they graduate, time-to-dropout if they drop out, or time to the end period if censored), and \mathbf{x}_i represents the individual characteristics. To account for the lack of graduation risk in the first two periods, we define another dummy variable: $f_i = 0$ if $t_i \leq 2$, and $f_i = 1$ otherwise. Let $j = 1$ represent the dropout risk and $j = 2$ represent the graduation risk. The individual likelihood is therefore:

$$L_i = \left[h_1(t_i | \mathbf{x}_i) S(t_i - 1 | \mathbf{x}_i) \right]^{(1-c_i)d_i} \times \left[h_2(t_i | \mathbf{x}_i) S(t_i - 1 | \mathbf{x}_i) \right]^{(1-c_i)(1-d_i)f_i} \times \left[S(t_i | \mathbf{x}_i) \right]^{c_i f_i},$$

where

$$S(t_i | \mathbf{x}_i) = \begin{cases} \prod_{k=1}^{t_i} (1 - h_1(k | \mathbf{x}_i)), & \text{if } t_i \leq 2 \\ \prod_{k=1}^2 (1 - h_1(k | \mathbf{x}_i)) \times \prod_{k=3}^{t_i} [(1 - h_1(k | \mathbf{x}_i)) \times (1 - h_2(k | \mathbf{x}_i))], & \text{if } 2 < t_i < T_i \\ \prod_{k=1}^2 (1 - h_1(k | \mathbf{x}_i)) \times \prod_{k=3}^{t_i-1} [(1 - h_1(k | \mathbf{x}_i)) \times (1 - h_2(k | \mathbf{x}_i))] \times (1 - h_2(T_i | \mathbf{x}_i)), & \text{if } t_i = T_i. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

T_i is the maximum possible duration for individual i , which is the duration from enrolment to the end of the data period. For example, for the 2011 cohort, $T_i = 11$.

The log-likelihood function is thus:

$$\begin{aligned}
\ln L &= \ln \left(\prod_{i=1}^N L_i \right) \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^N \ln L_i \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^N \left[(1 - c_i) d_i (\ln h_1(t_i | \mathbf{x}_i) + \ln S(t_i - 1 | \mathbf{x}_i)) \right. \\
&\quad \left. + (1 - c_i)(1 - d_i) f_i (\ln h_2(t_i | \mathbf{x}_i) + \ln S(t_i - 1 | \mathbf{x}_i)) + c_i f_i \ln S(t_i | \mathbf{x}_i) \right],
\end{aligned}$$

where $h_j(t_i | \mathbf{x}_i)$ is defined by equation (1), and $S(t_i | \mathbf{x}_i)$ is defined by equation (2).¹²

The individual characteristics \mathbf{x}_i include both time-invariant and time-varying variables. The time-invariant variables are indicators of characteristics at initial enrolment, such as entry cohort, gender, age, immigration status, field of study, and institution. The time-varying covariates include indicators for whether a student is enrolled full-time or part-time and whether they have changed their immigration status by obtaining permanent residency or citizenship.¹³ Although relatively rare, some students switch majors or institutions during their doctoral studies.¹⁴ We retain these students in our sample and account for these changes by including time-varying indicators for whether a student is currently in a major or institution different from their initial enrolment. We also include an indicator for the COVID-19 years (2019/2020 and onwards). Additionally, using data from the T1FF, we account for marital status, the number of children, and whether the student lives with their parents as part of the time-varying covariates.

We maximize the log-likelihood to obtain the estimates for β_1 , β_2 , γ_{1t} for $t = 1, \dots, 10$, and γ_{2t} for $t = 3, \dots, 11$. Given that the model is the discrete-time equivalent of the proportional hazards model and all covariates are dummy variables, the interpretation of β_1 and β_2 is

as follows: exponentiating each coefficient yields the hazard ratio relative to the reference group (Willett and Singer, 2003). A positive coefficient for a particular feature results in a hazard ratio greater than one, indicating a higher hazard rate compared to the reference group. This suggests that the event is more likely to occur, leading to a shorter time to the event for that group. Conversely, a negative coefficient yields a hazard ratio less than one, implying a lower hazard rate. This means the event is less likely to occur, resulting in a longer time to the event compared to the reference group. γ_{jt} represents the time effects, which will be discussed in detail in the next section.

4 Results

In this section, we present our estimation results. Table 2 displays selected estimated parameters for the baseline PSIS sample, with estimates for the dropout hazard function in column (1) and the graduation hazard function in column (2). Full estimation results, including standard errors, are provided in Table C1 of Appendix C.

Gender

As explained in the model section, when the explanatory variable is categorical, the interpretation of the coefficient is as follows: by exponentiating these estimates, we obtain the hazard ratios relative to the reference group. The estimates for the female dummy variable indicate that female doctoral students have a dropout hazard approximately 90 percent of that of male students, as $\exp(-0.102) = 0.9$, and a graduation hazard approximately 94 percent of that of male students, as $\exp(-0.067) = 0.94$. Female students are thus significantly less likely to drop out and less likely to graduate compared to their male counterparts, indicating a tendency for female students to remain enrolled longer.

Table 2: Estimation Results for Selected Variables (PSIS Sample)

	All		Male		Female	
	(1) Dropout	(2) Graduate	(3) Dropout	(4) Graduate	(5) Dropout	(6) Graduate
Cohort						
2011 cohort	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
2012 cohort	-0.040	-0.029*	0.001	-0.034	-0.078*	-0.024
2013 cohort	-0.035	-0.054***	0.028	-0.076***	-0.107**	-0.024
2014 cohort	-0.023	-0.084***	0.018	-0.107***	-0.063	-0.056
2015 cohort	0.013	-0.095***	0.072*	-0.147***	-0.051	-0.038
2016 cohort	-0.009	-0.123***	0.030	-0.181***	-0.054	-0.060
COVID	0.145***	0.004	0.068	0.044	0.236***	-0.042
Female	-0.102***	-0.067***				
Initial Immigration Status						
International student	-0.021	0.160***	-0.086***	0.203***	0.062*	0.107***
Permanent resident	0.129***	-0.021	0.118***	0.033	0.122***	-0.066**
Canadian citizen	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
Get PR/citizenship	-0.159***	-0.267***	-0.144**	-0.253***	-0.207***	-0.281***
Part-time	0.333***	-2.187***	0.311***	-2.043***	0.346***	-2.343***
Change major	-0.096	-0.191***	-0.141*	-0.234***	-0.060	-0.135***
Change school	-0.002	-0.792***	0.020	-0.778***	-0.049	-0.803***
Field of Study						
Education	0.125***	0.202***	0.039	0.310***	0.190***	0.147***
Visual and Performing Arts	0.207***	0.007	-0.030	0.220***	0.386***	-0.132**
Humanities	0.354***	-0.384***	0.203***	-0.229***	0.478***	-0.499***
Social and Behavioural Sciences	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
Business and Management	0.149***	0.004	0.111*	0.183***	0.151**	-0.138***
Physical and Life Sciences	-0.018	0.489***	-0.143***	0.545***	0.061	0.501***
Math and Computer Sciences	0.253***	0.340***	0.148***	0.421***	0.322***	0.316***
Agriculture	0.009	0.485***	-0.173**	0.607***	0.154**	0.424***
Health	0.054	0.517***	-0.137**	0.647***	0.175***	0.448***
Legal Studies	0.197***	-0.133**	0.021	0.090	0.339***	-0.318***
Architecture	0.300***	-0.134	0.100	0.025	0.452***	-0.222*
Engineering	0.040	0.540***	-0.064	0.620***	0.156***	0.505***
Multidisciplinary Studies	0.462***	0.118**	0.490***	0.142	0.437***	0.107
Log-likelihood	-129997.04		-69303.97		-60423.08	
Number of observations	356,380		185,980		170,400	

Notes: This table presents the maximum likelihood estimates of the duration model described in Section 3 for selected variables, using the baseline PSIS sample. Columns (1) and (2) provide estimates based on the full sample, while columns (3) through (6) present estimates separately by gender. Complete estimation results, including standard errors, are provided in Appendix C. As mandated by Statistics Canada, numbers of observations are rounded to the nearest ten.

*** significant at 1%; ** significant at 5%; * significant at 10%.

Source: Own calculation.

Female students may encounter unique challenges in their research environments that can hinder their progress. A recent study by [Bostwick and Weinberg \(2022\)](#) explores the impact of peer gender composition on doctoral completion rates, finding that women who join cohorts without female peers are less likely to graduate within six years compared to their male counterparts. To further explore gender heterogeneity, we estimate the model separately for men and women, with the corresponding results presented in columns (3) through (6) of Table 2. Complete estimation results by gender are available in Tables C2 and C3 of Appendix C. In the following discussion of the estimates for other covariates, we further examine the gender differences.

Year in Program

In our model, γ_{jt} captures the baseline hazard level for each period (year in program). Specifically, by substituting γ_{jt} into equation (1) with $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0}$,

$$h_j(t|\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0}) = 1 - \exp(-\exp(\gamma_{jt}))$$

represents the conditional probability that individuals in the baseline group—i.e., those whose covariate values are all zero—will experience event j in each time period, conditional on still being enrolled in the previous period.

Figure 1 plots the transformed $\hat{\gamma}_{jt}$, i.e., $1 - \exp(-\exp(\hat{\gamma}_{jt}))$, based on the baseline specification. Detailed estimates are provided in Appendix C. The probabilities in Figure 1 represent the hazard rate for individuals with $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{0}$ —specifically, a 25-year-old male Canadian citizen who began doctoral studies in social and behavioural sciences at the University of Toronto in 2011, studying full-time and unaffected by COVID. For this baseline group, for example, $\hat{\gamma}_{11} = -3.731$ indicates that the estimated conditional probability of dropout in the first year of study is $\hat{h}_{11} = 1 - \exp(-\exp(-3.731)) = 2.4\%$.

Figure 1: Fitted Baseline Graduation and Dropout Hazards by Year of Study

Note: This figure shows the baseline hazard levels for each year of study, representing the conditional probabilities of graduation and dropout for an individual with all covariates set to zero. Detailed estimates are provided in Appendix C.

Source: Own calculation, derived from columns (1) and (2) of Table C1 in Appendix C.

According to Figure 1, the conditional baseline dropout hazard remains fairly constant at around two percent during the first six years, with a noticeable increase beginning in the seventh year to approximately four to five percent. This suggests that students still enrolled by the seventh year or later face an increased risk of dropping out. Meanwhile, the baseline graduation hazard shows a sharp increase, rising from about 0.6 percent in the third year to around 24 percent in the sixth year, and continuing to climb to approximately 40 percent in the eighth year and beyond. Students in their sixth year or later are much more likely to graduate compared to those in earlier years. This time trend is similar for both men and women, as evidenced by the estimates in Tables C2 and C3 of Appendix C.

Entry Cohort

Since the 2011 cohort serves as the reference group, exponentiating the coefficients for the cohort indicators in Table 2 yields the hazard ratios for each cohort relative to the 2011 cohort, holding all other factors constant. The 2012 to 2016 cohorts (excluding the 2015 cohort) exhibit a slightly lower dropout hazard compared to the 2011 cohort, although these estimates are not statistically significant. However, the later cohorts show considerably lower graduation probabilities. For instance, the estimated coefficient for graduation for the 2016 cohort indicator is -0.123, which implies that the 2016 cohort has a graduation hazard 12 percent lower than that of the 2011 cohort. Estimation by gender (columns (4) and (6)) indicates that the decline in graduation rates across cohorts is driven by male students, as there are no significant cohort differences in the graduation hazard for female students.

In our analysis, we included an indicator variable for the years since the onset of COVID-19 (2019/2020 and onward). The significantly positive estimate for this variable, as shown in column (1), suggests that students experienced substantially higher dropout risks during the COVID years. Specifically, the dropout risk during the COVID years is approximately 16 percent higher. However, the estimates for graduation were not significant, indicating

that the likelihood of graduation remained relatively unchanged during the pandemic. In addition, the higher dropout hazard is primarily observed among female students: during COVID, their dropout risk increased by 27 percent.

Immigration Status

The model includes a set of time-invariant indicators for initial immigration status at the time of enrolment, as well as a time-varying indicator for obtaining permanent residency or citizenship. Estimates for initial immigration status in columns (1) and (2) show that, compared to Canadian citizens, permanent residents are 14 percent more likely to drop out, while international students are 17 percent more likely to graduate in each period. Additionally, we observe that once a student obtains permanent residency or citizenship, their dropout hazard is 15 percent lower, and their graduation hazard is 23 percent lower, compared to those with the same initial status who did not change their immigration status. Thus, obtaining permanent residency or citizenship is associated with a longer duration of study.

There are notable differences in patterns between men and women. For instance, male international students are nine percent less likely to drop out compared to male citizens, whereas female international students are six percent more likely to drop out compared to female citizens. Additionally, female permanent residents are significantly less likely to graduate compared to citizens.

Field of Study

Figure 2 shows the percentage difference in hazard for each field of study relative to the reference major—social and behavioural sciences—based on the baseline sample. The percentage difference in hazard is calculated by exponentiating the estimates and then subtracting one. The dropout and completion probabilities of doctoral students vary significantly across

Figure 2: Percentage Difference in Fitted Hazard Rates for Each Field of Study Relative to the Reference Major: Social and Behavioural Sciences

Note: This figure shows the percentage difference in fitted hazards for each field of study relative to the reference major, social and behavioural sciences, based on the baseline PSIS sample. The percentage difference in hazards is calculated by exponentiating the estimates and subtracting one. The majors are sorted in ascending order, from top to bottom, based on the estimates for graduation hazards.

Source: Own calculation, derived from columns (1) and (2) of Table 2.

different fields of study. Compared to students in the social and behavioural sciences, Ph.D. students in legal studies, architecture, and the humanities have a higher dropout hazard and a lower completion hazard. In contrast, those in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) and health-related fields exhibit significantly higher graduation probabilities. For instance, the graduation hazard is over 60 percent higher for students in agriculture, physical and life sciences, health, and engineering compared to students in social and behavioural sciences.

Previous literature has explored differences in the nature of doctoral studies across various fields. For example, [Golde \(2005\)](#) points out that STEM students typically conduct research

within groups or laboratories under the guidance of an advisor, whereas humanities students often engage in extensive independent research, requiring substantial reading and writing. This independence can result in longer completion times. Additionally, both [Golde \(2005\)](#) and [Ehrenberg and Mavros \(1995\)](#) note that humanities students often need to take on more teaching responsibilities to support themselves financially, given the limited funding opportunities compared to STEM fields. This additional workload may detract from their research progress by diverting time and energy away from their studies.

Post-graduation employment prospects may also influence doctoral completion rates. According to [Wall et al. \(2018\)](#), job and income prospects vary significantly across fields for doctoral students in Canada. On average, humanities students have much lower incomes than their STEM counterparts. [Roach and Sauermann \(2010\)](#) further finds that students in STEM and health-related fields generally encounter better job opportunities, both in academia and industry, providing a strong incentive to complete their degrees.

Examining the estimates by gender, we observe distinct patterns in both dropout and graduation hazards. In education, visual and performing arts, legal studies, and architecture, higher dropout hazards are driven by female students, whereas for male students, the dropout hazard is not significantly different from that of social and behavioural sciences. In physical and life sciences, agriculture, health, and engineering fields, men exhibit lower dropout hazards, while women display higher dropout hazards. The opposing trends by gender result in the estimates for the entire sample becoming statistically insignificant. Regarding graduation hazards: In both visual and performing arts and business and management fields, men exhibit significantly higher graduation hazards, while women have significantly lower graduation rates, rendering the estimates for the full sample insignificant. Female students also experience significantly lower graduation rates in legal studies and architecture compared to those in social and behavioural sciences.

Institution, Age, Part-time, and Switchers

The estimates for institution and age indicators are detailed in Appendix C. Compared to the University of Toronto, which enrolls the largest number of doctoral students, most other institutions show higher graduation rates, with many also exhibiting higher dropout risks. This suggests that students at the University of Toronto tend to remain enrolled longer. Interestingly, all six universities in Quebec also rank the lowest in terms of graduation hazard. Compared to the most common enrolment age of 25, older students are more likely to drop out and less likely to graduate.

Other estimates in Table 2 reveal that part-time students are about 40 percent more likely to drop out and 90 percent less likely to graduate compared to full-time students. Additionally, changing schools or majors is not associated with any significant change in dropout hazard. However, students who make such changes are significantly less likely to graduate. The decline in graduation hazard is notably larger for a change in institution compared to a change in major.¹⁵ All these patterns are largely consistent across genders.

Demographic Characteristics from the T1FF

To analyse the relationship between dropout or graduation and factors such as marital status, family composition, and number of children, we link the PSIS sample to the T1FF data. As noted earlier, not all individuals in our PSIS sample file taxes every year. For our estimation, we use a linked sample consisting of those who file taxes annually throughout their doctoral studies. Table 3 presents selected estimates for this linked sample, along with separate estimations by gender. Complete estimation results can be found in Appendix C.

Overall, most estimates remain consistent between the two specifications—without and with the inclusion of T1FF variables. However, some differences do emerge. Take the coefficient for immigration status, for instance. After linking to T1FF, the significance of

Table 3: Estimation Results for Selected Variables (PSIS Linked to T1FF Sample)

	All		Male		Female	
	(1) Dropout	(2) Graduate	(3) Dropout	(4) Graduate	(5) Dropout	(6) Graduate
Female	-0.132***	-0.070***				
Initial Immigration Status						
International student	-0.181***	0.161***	-0.227***	0.211***	-0.117**	0.087***
Permanent resident	0.118***	-0.055**	0.114***	-0.007	0.108**	-0.098**
Canadian citizen	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
Get PR/citizenship	-0.050	-0.273***	-0.022	-0.260***	-0.116	-0.279***
Married/Common law	-0.152***	0.151***	-0.173***	0.121***	-0.133***	0.173***
Live with parents	-0.111***	-0.147***	-0.030	-0.163***	-0.199***	-0.132***
Number of children						
No child	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
One child	0.142***	-0.170***	0.081	-0.046	0.201***	-0.304***
Two children	0.024	-0.138***	0.095*	0.008	-0.041	-0.289***
Three children	-0.012	-0.217***	-0.015	-0.050	-0.021	-0.388***
Four or more children	-0.047	-0.463***	0.060	-0.415***	-0.224	-0.339***
Log-likelihood	-82794.49		-42249.15		-40291.49	
Number of observations	235,000		116,740		118,260	

Notes: This table presents the maximum likelihood estimates of the duration model described in Section 3 for selected variables, using the PSIS-T1FF linked sample. Columns (1) and (2) provide estimates based on the full sample, while columns (3) through (6) present estimates separately by gender. Complete estimation results, including standard errors, are provided in Appendix C. As mandated by Statistics Canada, numbers of observations are rounded to the nearest ten.

*** significant at 1%; ** significant at 5%; * significant at 10%.

Source: Own calculation.

the dropout hazard for international students shifts from nonsignificant (-0.021 in column (1) of Table 2) to significantly negative (-0.181*** in column (1) of Table 3). A similar change is observed for the graduation hazard of permanent residents.

There are at least two possible reasons for this difference. First, the behaviour and outcomes could vary substantially between those who file taxes (and thus can be linked) and those who do not. International students have a considerably lower linkage rate (49 percent) compared to permanent residents (85 percent) and Canadian citizens (84 percent). To further investigate this, we extend the baseline specification for the PSIS sample by adding an interaction term between initial immigration status and an indicator for whether the sample can be linked to all T1FF years. The estimated coefficients for this interaction term are presented in Table 4. The results confirm distinct patterns based on linkage status. For instance, compared to linked citizens, unlinked citizens exhibit significantly lower dropout hazard as well as lower graduation hazard, a trend observed for both men and women.

The dropout hazard for linked international students is significantly lower, whereas for unlinked international students, it is marginally higher. Consequently, when the sample shifts from the PSIS sample to the PSIS-T1FF linked sample, the comparison changes from all international students and permanent residents relative to all Canadian citizens to linked international students and permanent residents relative to linked Canadian citizens. This shift alters the magnitude and significance of the coefficients.

Second, if immigration status is correlated with the newly added T1FF variables, including these variables could also affect the magnitude of the immigration status estimates. For example, the data show that permanent residents are more likely to be married and have more children compared to citizens, while international students are the least likely to live with their parents. These correlations also contribute to the differences in the immigration status estimates when comparing models with and without the T1FF variables.

Table 4: Estimation Results for Adding an Interaction Term (PSIS Sample)

	All		Male		Female	
	(1) Dropout	(2) Graduate	(3) Dropout	(4) Graduate	(5) Dropout	(6) Graduate
Initial Immigration Status \times PSIS-T1FF linkage						
International student, not linked	0.042*	0.025	-0.024	0.075***	0.136***	-0.042*
International student, linked	-0.150***	0.233***	-0.215***	0.278***	-0.079*	0.191***
Permanent resident, not linked	-0.050	-0.201***	-0.065	-0.163***	-0.071	-0.241***
Permanent resident, linked	0.138***	-0.032	0.130***	0.030	0.129***	-0.079**
Canadian citizen, not linked	-0.098***	-0.254***	-0.082*	-0.228***	-0.118**	-0.271***
Canadian citizen, linked	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
Log-likelihood	-129805.02		-69204.54		-60325.10	
Number of observations	356,380		185,980		170,400	

Notes: This table presents the maximum likelihood estimates of the duration model using the PSIS sample, incorporating an interaction term between initial immigration status and an indicator for PSIS-T1FF linkage into the baseline model. Columns (1) and (2) provide estimates based on the full sample, while columns (3) through (6) present estimates separately by gender. As mandated by Statistics Canada, numbers of observations are rounded to the nearest ten.

*** significant at 1%; ** significant at 5%; * significant at 10%.

Source: Own calculation.

Table 3 also reveals distinct patterns based on students' living arrangements and family responsibilities. Students who are married or in a common-law relationship exhibit significantly lower dropout rates and higher graduation rates, being approximately 15 percent less likely to drop out and 16 percent more likely to graduate compared to single students during each period. In contrast, students who live with their parents are less likely to drop out but also less likely to graduate, indicating that they tend to remain in school for extended periods.

When a student has one child, they are approximately 15 percent more likely to drop out and 16 percent less likely to graduate compared to students without children. However, having two or more children is not associated with higher dropout probabilities compared to those without children. Nonetheless, students with more children face significantly lower graduation rates. For instance, students with four or more children are 37 percent less likely

to graduate compared to those without children.

Separate estimations by gender reveal interesting patterns. Having children appears to affect male students much less; only when they have four or more children is their probability of graduation significantly reduced. In contrast, for female students, having children is correlated with a significantly lower probability of graduation, regardless of the number of children. While these results are not causal, they highlight that the impact of having children may differ substantially between male and female doctoral students.

5 Conclusion

Using Canadian administrative data, this paper estimates a duration model to study the graduation and dropout risks of doctoral students. We find that female students typically spend more time in their doctoral programs compared to male students with similar characteristics. We also find that international students exhibit significantly higher completion rates compared to citizens and permanent residents. If the government tightens visa restrictions or reduces the proportion of international students, it will likely negatively affect the production of highly skilled doctorates. Significant differences are also observed across fields of study. The humanities exhibit the lowest graduation hazard, whereas STEM and health-related majors tend to have higher completion hazard and lower dropout hazard.

Doctoral students and their educational and labour market outcomes are generally understudied in the literature. Given their importance and the substantial funding allocated to them, more research is needed to better understand this group. This paper offers the first evidence on graduation and dropout patterns among doctoral students in Canada, with its primary contribution being descriptive. A limitation of this study is that we do not address the underlying reasons behind our findings. However, we believe our results provide a

valuable starting point for future research to delve deeper into this group of students. For instance, our finding that obtaining permanent residency or citizenship is associated with longer study durations suggests avenues for further investigation. Establishing causal relationships and uncovering the mechanisms behind this finding could yield important policy insights to enhance the effectiveness of doctoral programs. Additionally, linking students to their subsequent earnings using the Education and Labour Market Longitudinal Platform could shed light on the labour market returns of doctoral studies in Canada, suggesting a direction for future research.

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Editorial Note

Michael Veall was recused from the editorial decision on this article.

Notes

¹Data used in this project were provided by Statistics Canada and accessed through one or more of the RDCs (Research Data Centre) in the Canadian Research Data Centre Network (CRDCN). Because of the confidential nature of these microdata, they cannot be shared. Researchers in Canada working at one of CRDCN’s member institutions can access the data at no additional cost to the researcher. Other researchers will have to pay cost-recovery to access the data. Access to the data is subject to a background check and research approval process. The protocols for data access, including fees for researchers at non-CRDCN institutions, can be found on the CRDCN website.

²A reporting year starts the day after the end of the institution’s previous winter term, which is usually in April, May, or June, and ends one year from this date. The PSIS codebook also refers to this as the “academic year.” In this paper, when we mention “year,” we are referring to the reporting year/academic year, unless specified otherwise.

³According to the PSIS codebook, the graduation year is defined as the year in which the student receives their degree upon completing the program. This is typically later than the time of the thesis defence for doctoral students.

⁴We determine the number of children a student has using two variables from the T1FF dataset: whether the individual is classified as a child of the family and the total number of children in the family. If the student is classified as a child, their number of children is set to zero. Otherwise, it equals the total number of children in the family. This approach is the same as the one used in [Gervais, Liu and Lochner \(2023\)](#).

⁵ We have also attempted to include these students in our estimation, but the estimates for the first two years of graduation are very noisy and have large standard errors. Thus, we have decided to exclude these rare cases from our study.

⁶As required by Statistics Canada, the number of observations should be rounded to the nearest ten.

⁷The PSIS data is reported by academic year, whereas the T1FF data is reported by calendar year. To align them, we link each PSIS record to the T1FF record for the calendar year in which the academic year begins.

⁸Allowing gaps in T1FF data would create inconsistencies and lead to comparability issues between analyses based solely on the PSIS sample and those using the PSIS-T1FF linked sample. For instance, if an individual has complete data in the PSIS but gaps in the T1FF data due to not filing taxes in certain years, analyses based on PSIS variables would include all years of observation, while analyses involving T1FF variables would only include the years when tax data is available.

⁹As required by Statistics Canada, both the numerator and the denominator of fractions are rounded to the nearest ten.

¹⁰This method is the same as used in [Gervais, Liu and Lochner \(2023\)](#).

¹¹While the PSIS includes a variable for the program end date, it is often missing for doctoral students who cease to appear in the data. Thus, we believe our imputation method more accurately captures dropout rates. However, because there are gaps in the data, it is also possible that the student has a gap and would be back again. This would overestimate the dropout rates, especially for later cohorts who are observed for a relatively short period. Among the 2011 cohort, which we observe for up to 11 years, conditional on having one year missing, approximately five percent return, while the remaining 95 percent do not. This suggests

that the extent of overestimation is relatively small.

¹²For individuals with gaps, the conditional graduation and dropout hazards for the gap years are set to zero because the individual is observed again in the data after the gap. Specifically, $h_j(t|\mathbf{x}_i) = 0$ if year t is missing for individual i , where $j \in \{1, 2\}$. The survivor function $S(t_i|\mathbf{x}_i)$ can be calculated accordingly as defined by equation (2).

¹³Specifically, this indicator takes the value of one from the point at which an international student becomes a permanent resident or citizen, or when a permanent resident becomes a citizen, and remains one thereafter. In the baseline PSIS sample, approximately 19.3 percent of students who began as international students obtained PR or citizenship during their studies. Additionally, about 9.7 percent of students who started as PRs became citizens.

¹⁴In our sample, approximately four percent of students change their major group, while three percent change their institution.

¹⁵The estimation results, excluding individuals who changed their major or school, remain similar and are available upon request.

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Appendix A Sample Size by Cohort and Province

Table A1 reports the number of doctoral students by starting year and study province. In accordance with Statistics Canada’s requirements, the number of observations is rounded to the nearest ten. Additionally, institution-level statistics for Newfoundland and Labrador (NL), Prince Edward Island (PEI), and Manitoba (MB) are not releasable. Since NL and PEI each have only one institution with doctoral students—the Memorial University of Newfoundland in NL and the University of Prince Edward Island in PEI—and since the majority of students in MB are enrolled at the University of Manitoba, province-level statistics are (almost) equivalent to institution-level statistics. Therefore, these three provinces are excluded from this table. However, these institutions are included in our sample and estimations. As a result, the sum of the observations listed in Table A1 does not match the total sample size.

Table A1: Number of Students by Starting Year and Study Province

Cohort	Nova Scotia	New Brunswick	Quebec	Ontario	Saskatchewan	Alberta	British Columbia
2011	150	100	3140	4040	270	1020	1260
2012	160	90	3220	4120	280	1060	1130
2013	140	100	3220	4100	260	980	1080
2014	160	90	3220	4010	260	1000	920
2015	130	100	3250	4180	230	1070	1070
2016	150	80	3400	3970	300	1050	1010

Notes: This table reports the number of doctoral students by starting year (cohort) and study province. As mandated by Statistics Canada, numbers of observations are rounded to the nearest ten. Due to confidentiality requirements, sample sizes for Newfoundland and Labrador, Prince Edward Island, and Manitoba are not disclosed.

Source: Author’s calculation.

Appendix B Field of Study Grouping

Table B1 presents the PSIS primary grouping (CIPPG) of fields of study, along with our adjustments and re-grouping using the provided two-digit and four-digit codes. Due to small sample sizes, we have excluded the Personal, Protective, and Transportation Services categories, as well as the Unclassified category. Additionally, not all groupings have Ph.D. students. Our sample comprises a total of 13 major groupings: Education; Visual and Performing Arts, and Communications Technologies; Humanities; Social and Behavioural Sciences; Business, Management, and Public Administration; Physical and Life Sciences, and Technologies; Mathematics, Computer, and Information Sciences; Agriculture, Natural Resources, and Conservation; Health and Related Fields; Legal Professions and Studies; Architecture and Related Studies; Engineering and Engineering-Related Fields; and Other Multidisciplinary Studies.

Table B1: Field of Study Classification

PSIS original grouping (CIPPG)	Our adjustment and grouping
001.Personal improvement and leisure	Combine CIP 2-digit codes 21 (Pre-technology education/pre-industrial arts programs) and 53 (High school/secondary diploma and certificate programs) within CIPPG code 120 with CIPPG code 001
010.Education	Same
020.Visual and performing arts, and communications technologies	Same
030.Humanities	Same
040.Social and behavioural sciences and law	Group CIP 2-digit code 22 (Legal professions and studies) within CIPPG code 040 into a separate category (Legal professions and studies)
	Group all other (i.e., except CIP 2-digit code 22) within CIPPG code 040 into a separate category (Social and behavioural sciences)
050.Business, management and public administration	Same
060.Physical and life sciences and technologies	Same
070.Mathematics, computer and information sciences	Same
080.Architecture, engineering, and related technologies	Group CIP 2-digit code 04 (Architecture and related services) and CIP 4-digit code 30.12 (Historic preservation & conservation) within CIPPG code 080 into a separate category (Architecture and related studies)
	Group CIP 2-digit codes 14 (Engineering) and 15 (Engineering tech. and engineering-related fields) within CIPPG code 080 into a separate category (Engineering and engineering-related fields)
	Group CIP 2-digit codes 46 (Construction trades), 47 (Mechanic & repair tech), and 48 (Precision production) within CIPPG code 080 into a separate category (Trades and related studies)
090.Agriculture, natural resources and conservation	Same
100.Health and related fields	Same
110.Personal, protective and transportation services	Same
120.Other	Combine CIP 2-digit codes 21 (Pre-technology education/pre-industrial arts programs) and 53 (High school/secondary diploma and certificate programs) within CIPPG code 120 with CIPPG code 001
	Group CIP 4-digit code 30.99 (Multidisciplinary/interdisciplinary studies, other) within CIPPG code 120 into a separate category (Multidisciplinary studies, other)
500.Unclassified	Same

Notes: This table presents the PSIS primary grouping (CIPPG) of fields of study, along with our adjustments and re-grouping using the provided two-digit and four-digit codes.

Source: Gervais, Liu, and Lochner (2023).

Appendix C Estimation Results

Table C1 presents the maximum likelihood estimates of the duration model described in Section 3. Columns (1) and (2) contain estimates using the PSIS sample, while columns (3) and (4) feature estimates from the PSIS linked to the T1FF sample, which incorporates additional covariates. Standard errors are shown in brackets adjacent to the point estimates. Tables C2 and C3 present the estimates separately for men and women.

According to the vetting guidelines set by Statistics Canada, institution-level statistics for institutions in Newfoundland and Labrador, Prince Edward Island, and Manitoba are not releasable and are thus excluded from this table. However, these institutions are included in our estimations. Other than the institutions in those three provinces, institutions that have doctoral students but are not listed are grouped under the “Other Universities” category. Institutions are ranked by their estimates of graduation hazards (column (2)) in the baseline specification, from largest to smallest.

Table C1: Complete Estimation Results (Male and Female)

	PSIS sample only		PSIS linked to T1FF sample	
	(1) Dropout	(2) Graduate	(3) Dropout	(4) Graduate
Time/Year in Program				
γ_{j1} (Year 1)	-3.731(0.053)***		-3.663(0.066)***	
γ_{j2} (Year 2)	-3.485(0.052)***		-3.462(0.066)***	
γ_{j3} (Year 3)	-3.791(0.054)***	-5.123(0.054)***	-3.789(0.067)***	-4.950(0.065)***
γ_{j4} (Year 4)	-4.078(0.055)***	-3.482(0.035)***	-4.050(0.069)***	-3.328(0.045)***
γ_{j5} (Year 5)	-3.934(0.055)***	-2.075(0.030)***	-3.908(0.069)***	-1.949(0.040)***
γ_{j6} (Year 6)	-3.727(0.058)***	-1.277(0.029)***	-3.715(0.072)***	-1.206(0.039)***
γ_{j7} (Year 7)	-3.099(0.059)***	-0.910(0.029)***	-3.171(0.074)***	-0.860(0.040)***
γ_{j8} (Year 8)	-3.042(0.070)***	-0.714(0.033)***	-3.057(0.085)***	-0.677(0.045)***
γ_{j9} (Year 9)	-2.974(0.089)***	-0.664(0.040)***	-3.050(0.109)***	-0.610(0.057)***
γ_{j10} (Year 10)	-2.988(0.134)***	-0.647(0.052)***	-3.124(0.168)***	-0.620(0.086)***
γ_{j11} (Year 11)		-0.573(0.076)***		
Cohort				
2011 cohort	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
2012 cohort	-0.040(0.029)	-0.029(0.017)*	-0.061(0.034)*	-0.041(0.021)*
2013 cohort	-0.035(0.029)	-0.054(0.019)***	-0.042(0.035)	-0.064(0.024)***

2014 cohort	-0.023(0.031)	-0.084(0.023)***	-0.067(0.037)*	-0.128(0.029)***
2015 cohort	0.013(0.032)	-0.095(0.027)***	-0.037(0.038)	-0.164(0.037)***
2016 cohort	-0.009(0.034)	-0.123(0.032)***	-0.088(0.041)**	-0.210(0.046)***
COVID	0.145(0.033)***	0.004(0.021)	0.171(0.039)***	0.018(0.026)
Female	-0.102(0.018)***	-0.067(0.011)***	-0.132(0.022)***	-0.070(0.015)***
Initial Immigration Status				
International student	-0.021(0.021)	0.160(0.013)***	-0.181(0.031)***	0.161(0.019)***
Permanent resident	0.129(0.029)***	-0.021(0.021)	0.118(0.032)***	-0.055(0.026)**
Canadian citizen	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
Get PR/citizenship	-0.159(0.048)***	-0.267(0.019)***	-0.050(0.058)	-0.273(0.026)***
Part-time	0.333(0.034)***	-2.187(0.056)***	0.317(0.038)***	-2.252(0.072)***
Change major	-0.096(0.060)	-0.191(0.033)***	-0.141(0.074)*	-0.244(0.046)***
Change institution	-0.002(0.061)	-0.792(0.040)***	0.054(0.075)	-0.841(0.059)***
Field of Study				
Education	0.125(0.039)***	0.202(0.030)***	0.211(0.044)***	0.209(0.038)***
Visual and Performing Arts	0.207(0.054)***	0.007(0.041)	0.319(0.065)***	0.012(0.057)
Humanities	0.354(0.033)***	-0.384(0.027)***	0.412(0.039)***	-0.416(0.036)***
Social and Behavioural Sciences	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
Business and Management	0.149(0.044)***	0.004(0.034)	0.199(0.050)***	-0.081(0.045)*
Physical and Life Sciences	-0.018(0.031)	0.489(0.018)***	0.025(0.038)	0.523(0.023)***
Mathematics and Computer Sciences	0.253(0.042)***	0.340(0.026)***	0.345(0.051)***	0.315(0.035)***
Agriculture	0.009(0.056)	0.485(0.032)***	0.093(0.069)	0.465(0.042)***
Health	0.054(0.038)	0.517(0.022)***	0.125(0.043)***	0.517(0.028)***
Legal Studies	0.197(0.069)***	-0.133(0.062)**	0.200(0.086)**	-0.118(0.088)
Architecture	0.300(0.102)***	-0.134(0.092)	0.383(0.116)***	-0.241(0.129)*
Engineering	0.040(0.032)	0.540(0.019)***	0.111(0.039)***	0.549(0.025)***
Multidisciplinary Studies	0.462(0.072)***	0.118(0.059)**	0.549(0.082)***	0.092(0.076)
Institution				
Saint Mary's University	-0.162(0.280)	1.549(0.153)***	-0.259(0.337)	1.345(0.196)***
University of Calgary	0.474(0.052)***	0.820(0.030)***	0.403(0.065)***	0.921(0.037)***
Acadia University	0.262(0.197)	0.775(0.175)***	0.375(0.206)*	0.586(0.213)***
University of Guelph	0.057(0.081)	0.737(0.040)***	0.138(0.092)	0.715(0.049)***
Laurentian University	0.215(0.152)	0.698(0.099)***	0.273(0.166)	0.734(0.120)***
Brock University	-0.219(0.186)	0.687(0.091)***	-0.126(0.204)	0.575(0.114)***
McMaster University	0.336(0.059)***	0.671(0.032)***	0.288(0.072)***	0.688(0.040)***
University of Western Ontario	0.040(0.056)	0.655(0.029)***	0.121(0.065)*	0.644(0.035)***
University of Northern British Columbia	0.490(0.115)***	0.655(0.072)***	0.609(0.133)***	0.670(0.091)***
Lakehead University	0.287(0.172)*	0.628(0.096)***	0.530(0.178)***	0.554(0.125)***
Toronto Metropolitan University	0.265(0.093)***	0.575(0.053)***	0.259(0.107)**	0.622(0.064)***
University of Victoria	0.304(0.074)***	0.575(0.044)***	0.353(0.090)***	0.495(0.057)***
Ontario Tech University	0.030(0.166)	0.570(0.092)***	0.083(0.191)	0.554(0.119)***
Wilfrid Laurier University	0.028(0.127)	0.553(0.083)***	0.081(0.141)	0.536(0.101)***
University of Windsor	0.052(0.117)	0.544(0.059)***	0.068(0.134)	0.518(0.071)***
University of Alberta	0.301(0.049)***	0.525(0.027)**	0.300(0.061)***	0.511(0.034)***
University of Lethbridge	0.483(0.186)***	0.490(0.112)***	0.292(0.253)	0.633(0.141)***
Queen's University	-0.061(0.074)	0.478(0.036)***	-0.067(0.089)	0.479(0.045)***
University of Saskatchewan	0.261(0.071)***	0.474(0.039)***	0.234(0.086)***	0.478(0.048)***
University of Waterloo	0.081(0.058)	0.441(0.030)***	0.178(0.072)**	0.435(0.041)***
Carleton University	0.540(0.060)***	0.400(0.044)***	0.585(0.070)***	0.294(0.058)***
University of Moncton	0.598(0.192)***	0.346(0.135)**	0.695(0.217)***	0.301(0.165)*

Dalhousie University	-0.174(0.106)	0.338(0.048)***	-0.190(0.130)	0.436(0.059)***
Simon Fraser University	0.032(0.070)	0.275(0.038)***	0.021(0.085)	0.307(0.049)***
University of Ottawa	0.132(0.054)**	0.267(0.032)***	0.204(0.064)***	0.240(0.041)***
University of British Columbia	0.067(0.049)	0.237(0.026)***	0.118(0.060)**	0.238(0.033)***
Trent University	0.132(0.174)	0.138(0.113)	0.036(0.218)	0.058(0.149)
Other Universities	0.616(0.046)***	0.138(0.031)***	0.703(0.054)***	0.063(0.043)
University of New Brunswick	0.201(0.101)**	0.128(0.069)*	0.277(0.117)**	0.065(0.096)
York University	0.484(0.051)***	0.116(0.040)***	0.519(0.060)***	0.055(0.052)
University of Northern British Columbia	0.085(0.271)	0.115(0.156)	0.131(0.293)	0.082(0.179)
University of Sherbrooke	0.955(0.046)***	0.097(0.038)**	1.092(0.053)***	-0.130(0.054)**
Laval University	0.678(0.044)***	0.052(0.030)*	0.770(0.053)***	0.003(0.042)
University of Montreal	0.526(0.041)***	0.044(0.027)	0.560(0.050)***	-0.094(0.037)***
McGill University	0.169(0.048)***	0.018(0.026)	0.184(0.061)***	-0.051(0.037)
University of Toronto	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
Concordia University	0.036(0.064)	-0.032(0.039)	0.043(0.081)	-0.099(0.056)*
University of Quebec in Montreal	0.546(0.052)***	-0.514(0.046)***	0.578(0.061)***	-0.768(0.064)***
Age when first enrol				
21	0.349(0.215)	-0.148(0.130)	0.628(0.246)**	-0.228(0.186)
22	-0.065(0.078)	0.084(0.038)**	-0.106(0.095)	0.046(0.050)
23	-0.042(0.051)	0.111(0.025)***	-0.032(0.063)	0.137(0.033)***
24	-0.116(0.043)***	0.116(0.020)***	-0.134(0.053)**	0.149(0.026)***
25	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
26	0.094(0.040)**	-0.080(0.020)***	0.156(0.050)***	-0.087(0.027)***
27	0.180(0.041)***	-0.153(0.022)***	0.233(0.052)***	-0.141(0.030)***
28	0.249(0.043)***	-0.217(0.024)***	0.276(0.054)***	-0.206(0.032)***
29	0.259(0.046)***	-0.254(0.027)***	0.269(0.058)***	-0.252(0.036)***
30	0.306(0.047)***	-0.348(0.029)***	0.362(0.059)***	-0.337(0.039)***
31	0.396(0.049)***	-0.370(0.032)***	0.423(0.061)***	-0.366(0.043)***
32	0.348(0.053)***	-0.357(0.035)***	0.353(0.066)***	-0.326(0.046)***
33	0.426(0.055)***	-0.397(0.038)***	0.480(0.067)***	-0.391(0.052)***
34	0.473(0.057)***	-0.429(0.042)***	0.438(0.070)***	-0.418(0.054)***
35	0.492(0.059)***	-0.424(0.045)***	0.582(0.070)***	-0.365(0.059)***
36	0.468(0.063)***	-0.381(0.046)***	0.537(0.074)***	-0.322(0.061)***
37	0.523(0.064)***	-0.492(0.051)***	0.556(0.076)***	-0.444(0.068)***
38	0.430(0.069)***	-0.441(0.053)***	0.482(0.081)***	-0.357(0.067)***
39	0.470(0.070)***	-0.377(0.055)***	0.526(0.081)***	-0.324(0.070)***
40	0.431(0.074)***	-0.522(0.059)***	0.488(0.086)***	-0.439(0.076)***
41	0.491(0.074)***	-0.380(0.062)***	0.449(0.086)***	-0.334(0.075)***
42	0.446(0.079)***	-0.400(0.063)***	0.404(0.094)***	-0.309(0.079)***
43	0.564(0.076)***	-0.462(0.064)***	0.632(0.087)***	-0.390(0.079)***
44	0.502(0.083)***	-0.499(0.073)***	0.536(0.095)***	-0.478(0.091)***
45	0.434(0.089)***	-0.509(0.073)***	0.441(0.101)***	-0.518(0.092)***
46	0.623(0.085)***	-0.451(0.079)***	0.653(0.098)***	-0.353(0.096)***
47	0.658(0.087)***	-0.502(0.085)***	0.690(0.098)***	-0.411(0.102)***
48	0.695(0.094)***	-0.530(0.089)***	0.747(0.107)***	-0.515(0.111)***
49	0.692(0.094)***	-0.592(0.094)***	0.721(0.106)***	-0.413(0.109)***
50	0.740(0.093)***	-0.629(0.096)***	0.674(0.113)***	-0.566(0.117)***
51	0.854(0.094)***	-0.386(0.099)***	0.873(0.106)***	-0.279(0.117)**
52	0.734(0.103)***	-0.344(0.102)***	0.801(0.115)***	-0.345(0.125)***
53	0.773(0.107)***	-0.650(0.111)***	0.868(0.116)***	-0.594(0.137)***
54	0.827(0.115)***	-0.396(0.122)***	0.838(0.131)***	-0.243(0.140)*
55	0.545(0.124)***	-0.405(0.121)***	0.585(0.142)***	-0.404(0.156)***
Married/Common law			-0.152(0.026)***	0.151(0.017)***

Live with parents		-0.111(0.037)***	-0.147(0.026)***
Number of Children			
No child		(base)	(base)
One child		0.142(0.033)***	-0.170(0.022)***
Two children		0.024(0.037)	-0.138(0.026)***
Three children		-0.012(0.054)	-0.217(0.041)***
Four or more children		-0.047(0.083)	-0.463(0.067)***
Log-likelihood	-129997.04		-82794.49
Number of observations ^a	356,380		235,000

Note: This table presents the maximum likelihood estimates of the duration model described in Section 3. Columns (1) and (2) contain estimates using the PSIS sample, while columns (3) and (4) feature estimates from the PSIS linked to the T1FF sample, which incorporates additional covariates. Standard errors are shown in brackets adjacent to the point estimates.

^aAs mandated by Statistics Canada, numbers of observations are rounded to the nearest ten.

*** $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.1$.

Source: Author's calculation.

Table C2: Complete Estimation Results (Male)

	PSIS sample only		PSIS linked to T1FF sample	
	(1) Dropout	(2) Graduate	(3) Dropout	(4) Graduate
Time/Year in Program				
γ_{j1} (Year 1)	-3.577(0.072)***		-3.592(0.092)***	
γ_{j2} (Year 2)	-3.310(0.071)***		-3.366(0.091)***	
γ_{j3} (Year 3)	-3.694(0.073)***	-5.248(0.073)***	-3.797(0.094)***	-5.058(0.089)***
γ_{j4} (Year 4)	-3.950(0.075)***	-3.546(0.048)***	-3.985(0.095)***	-3.393(0.063)***
γ_{j5} (Year 5)	-3.745(0.075)***	-2.156(0.042)***	-3.765(0.096)***	-2.027(0.057)***
γ_{j6} (Year 6)	-3.544(0.079)***	-1.393(0.041)***	-3.583(0.100)***	-1.343(0.055)***
γ_{j7} (Year 7)	-2.852(0.080)***	-1.056(0.042)***	-3.027(0.103)***	-1.025(0.057)***
γ_{j8} (Year 8)	-2.765(0.095)***	-0.900(0.046)***	-2.834(0.118)***	-0.846(0.064)***
γ_{j9} (Year 9)	-2.820(0.128)***	-0.865(0.057)***	-2.910(0.157)***	-0.784(0.083)***
γ_{j10} (Year 10)	-2.881(0.201)***	-0.865(0.075)***	-3.137(0.262)***	-0.858(0.130)***
γ_{j11} (Year 11)		-0.638(0.107)***		
Cohort				
2011 cohort	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
2012 cohort	0.001(0.039)	-0.034(0.023)	-0.026(0.048)	-0.045(0.029)
2013 cohort	0.028(0.040)	-0.076(0.025)***	0.040(0.049)	-0.074(0.033)**
2014 cohort	0.018(0.042)	-0.107(0.031)***	-0.019(0.051)	-0.144(0.040)***
2015 cohort	0.072(0.044)*	-0.147(0.037)***	0.033(0.053)	-0.196(0.050)***
2016 cohort	0.030(0.046)	-0.181(0.042)***	-0.027(0.057)	-0.272(0.063)***
COVID	0.068(0.045)	0.044(0.028)	0.081(0.055)	0.041(0.036)
Initial Immigration Status				
International student	-0.086(0.028)***	0.203(0.017)***	-0.227(0.041)***	0.211(0.026)***
Permanent resident	0.118(0.039)***	0.033(0.029)	0.114(0.043)***	-0.007(0.036)
Canadian citizen	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
Get PR/citizenship	-0.144(0.063)**	-0.253(0.025)***	-0.022(0.076)	-0.260(0.034)***
Part-time	0.311(0.049)***	-2.043(0.076)***	0.279(0.055)***	-2.144(0.101)***

Change major	-0.141(0.083)*	-0.234(0.046)***	-0.174(0.103)*	-0.318(0.066)***
Change institution	0.020(0.080)	-0.778(0.053)***	0.115(0.100)	-0.886(0.083)***
Field of Study				
Education	0.039(0.063)	0.310(0.053)***	0.177(0.071)**	0.267(0.069)***
Visual and Performing Arts	-0.030(0.083)	0.220(0.060)***	0.082(0.101)	0.167(0.085)**
Humanities	0.203(0.047)***	-0.229(0.039)***	0.268(0.056)***	-0.264(0.053)***
Social and Behavioural Sciences	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
Business and Management	0.111(0.060)*	0.183(0.049)***	0.166(0.071)**	0.141(0.065)**
Physical and Life Sciences	-0.143(0.043)***	0.545(0.028)***	-0.086(0.053)	0.595(0.036)***
Mathematics and Computer Sciences	0.148(0.052)***	0.421(0.035)***	0.250(0.064)***	0.380(0.047)***
Agriculture	-0.173(0.082)**	0.607(0.047)***	-0.092(0.101)	0.587(0.062)***
Health	-0.137(0.061)**	0.647(0.036)***	-0.142(0.074)*	0.706(0.046)***
Legal Studies	0.021(0.100)	0.090(0.085)	0.084(0.120)	0.014(0.123)
Architecture	0.100(0.163)	0.025(0.138)	0.157(0.189)	-0.055(0.197)
Engineering	-0.064(0.041)	0.620(0.028)***	0.002(0.051)	0.635(0.036)***
Multidisciplinary Studies	0.490(0.103)***	0.142(0.100)	0.544(0.121)***	0.161(0.130)
Institution				
Saint Mary's University	0.087(0.358)	1.504(0.241)***	-0.006(0.452)	1.446(0.302)***
Acadia University	0.104(0.243)	0.940(0.208)***	0.241(0.254)	0.733(0.260)***
University of Calgary	0.329(0.073)***	0.815(0.041)***	0.221(0.096)**	0.923(0.053)***
University of Northern British Columbia	0.474(0.155)***	0.725(0.099)***	0.582(0.185)***	0.840(0.129)***
Laurentian University	0.083(0.230)	0.725(0.140)***	0.243(0.245)	0.751(0.181)***
Brock University	-0.042(0.254)	0.699(0.136)***	-0.035(0.294)	0.643(0.176)***
McMaster University	0.306(0.078)***	0.688(0.044)***	0.244(0.097)**	0.692(0.055)***
University of Victoria	0.200(0.103)*	0.675(0.058)***	0.255(0.131)*	0.636(0.077)***
University of Western Ontario	-0.060(0.077)	0.656(0.039)***	0.001(0.091)	0.650(0.050)***
University of Guelph	-0.016(0.118)	0.627(0.059)***	0.088(0.132)	0.580(0.073)***
University of Windsor	0.093(0.151)	0.595(0.082)***	0.106(0.177)	0.531(0.103)***
Wilfrid Laurier University	-0.089(0.191)	0.592(0.130)***	0.021(0.201)	0.579(0.153)***
Ontario Tech University	-0.013(0.189)	0.581(0.107)***	0.045(0.222)	0.516(0.143)***
University of Alberta	0.273(0.067)***	0.567(0.037)***	0.279(0.083)***	0.551(0.048)***
Lakehead University	-0.081(0.293)	0.529(0.135)***	0.219(0.308)	0.471(0.183)**
Toronto Metropolitan University	0.411(0.113)***	0.527(0.073)***	0.350(0.133)***	0.558(0.087)***
University of Saskatchewan	0.233(0.095)**	0.524(0.053)***	0.208(0.118)*	0.512(0.067)***
University of Lethbridge	0.066(0.292)	0.493(0.143)***	-0.531(0.503)	0.660(0.183)***
University of Waterloo	-0.039(0.075)	0.487(0.038)***	0.028(0.094)	0.445(0.052)***
Queen's University	-0.197(0.101)*	0.462(0.049)***	-0.150(0.120)	0.484(0.062)***
Carleton University	0.471(0.079)***	0.431(0.058)***	0.492(0.096)***	0.314(0.079)***
Trent University	0.381(0.236)	0.372(0.177)**	0.072(0.324)	0.248(0.241)
Dalhousie University	-0.258(0.140)*	0.325(0.064)***	-0.408(0.184)**	0.412(0.078)***
University of British Columbia	0.078(0.065)	0.321(0.035)***	0.158(0.081)*	0.328(0.046)***
Simon Fraser University	-0.076(0.098)	0.296(0.052)***	-0.082(0.119)	0.321(0.066)***
University of Ottawa	0.097(0.074)	0.286(0.044)***	0.145(0.088)	0.284(0.058)***
York University	0.381(0.074)***	0.144(0.060)**	0.460(0.089)***	0.097(0.081)
University of Sherbrooke	0.840(0.064)***	0.138(0.051)***	0.990(0.076)***	-0.128(0.077)*
Other Universities	0.448(0.063)***	0.118(0.043)***	0.526(0.076)***	0.003(0.062)
University of New Brunswick	0.249(0.130)*	0.111(0.094)	0.312(0.158)**	-0.055(0.139)
University of Montreal	0.469(0.055)***	0.107(0.037)***	0.514(0.068)***	-0.002(0.051)
Laval University	0.597(0.060)***	0.101(0.042)**	0.716(0.074)***	0.008(0.060)
McGill University	0.069(0.065)	0.043(0.036)	0.089(0.087)	-0.031(0.052)
University of Northern British Columbia	0.261(0.323)	0.030(0.218)	0.261(0.362)	-0.014(0.237)
Concordia University	0.039(0.083)	0.017(0.051)	0.111(0.104)	-0.055(0.074)

University of Moncton	1.028(0.247)***	0.001(0.254)	1.088(0.283)***	-0.312(0.320)
University of Toronto	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
University of Quebec in Montreal	0.577(0.073)***	-0.310(0.071)***	0.593(0.087)***	-0.468(0.098)***
Age when first enrol				
21	0.448(0.319)	-0.041(0.184)	0.777(0.383)**	-0.135(0.264)
22	0.132(0.114)	-0.052(0.059)	0.154(0.141)	-0.104(0.080)
23	0.028(0.070)	0.061(0.034)*	0.086(0.087)	0.089(0.046)*
24	-0.081(0.058)	0.108(0.027)***	-0.072(0.074)	0.143(0.036)***
25	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
26	0.053(0.054)	-0.095(0.027)***	0.137(0.070)**	-0.099(0.037)***
27	0.197(0.056)***	-0.159(0.030)***	0.271(0.072)***	-0.148(0.040)***
28	0.251(0.058)***	-0.218(0.032)***	0.330(0.075)***	-0.218(0.044)***
29	0.250(0.063)***	-0.207(0.035)***	0.361(0.080)***	-0.231(0.049)***
30	0.331(0.064)***	-0.313(0.038)***	0.444(0.083)***	-0.330(0.053)***
31	0.349(0.067)***	-0.330(0.042)***	0.414(0.087)***	-0.347(0.058)***
32	0.373(0.072)***	-0.336(0.046)***	0.473(0.091)***	-0.365(0.064)***
33	0.389(0.075)***	-0.399(0.050)***	0.516(0.094)***	-0.448(0.072)***
34	0.403(0.079)***	-0.422(0.056)***	0.405(0.100)***	-0.504(0.075)***
35	0.519(0.080)***	-0.452(0.059)***	0.669(0.098)***	-0.464(0.081)***
36	0.370(0.088)***	-0.383(0.062)***	0.511(0.106)***	-0.347(0.085)***
37	0.508(0.086)***	-0.540(0.069)***	0.558(0.107)***	-0.526(0.093)***
38	0.452(0.095)***	-0.435(0.073)***	0.499(0.118)***	-0.461(0.095)***
39	0.444(0.097)***	-0.469(0.078)***	0.618(0.112)***	-0.458(0.103)***
40	0.447(0.100)***	-0.638(0.083)***	0.506(0.121)***	-0.643(0.111)***
41	0.590(0.099)***	-0.570(0.094)***	0.649(0.115)***	-0.571(0.116)***
42	0.508(0.107)***	-0.470(0.092)***	0.518(0.129)***	-0.386(0.113)***
43	0.634(0.102)***	-0.587(0.093)***	0.764(0.119)***	-0.566(0.120)***
44	0.557(0.114)***	-0.600(0.108)***	0.634(0.134)***	-0.644(0.139)***
45	0.431(0.122)***	-0.622(0.107)***	0.506(0.140)***	-0.687(0.137)***
46	0.552(0.127)***	-0.526(0.118)***	0.622(0.147)***	-0.538(0.146)***
47	0.795(0.117)***	-0.624(0.133)***	0.869(0.133)***	-0.569(0.165)***
48	0.870(0.128)***	-0.640(0.143)***	0.936(0.152)***	-0.664(0.182)***
49	0.608(0.143)***	-0.875(0.155)***	0.697(0.166)***	-0.727(0.187)***
50	0.851(0.124)***	-0.713(0.145)***	0.885(0.150)***	-0.604(0.174)***
51	0.759(0.140)***	-0.397(0.156)**	0.877(0.156)***	-0.316(0.186)*
52	0.682(0.151)***	-0.607(0.164)***	0.834(0.170)***	-0.653(0.202)***
53	0.765(0.165)***	-0.612(0.188)***	0.900(0.177)***	-0.565(0.222)**
54	1.009(0.165)***	-0.316(0.204)	1.014(0.200)***	-0.233(0.225)
55	0.601(0.171)***	-0.351(0.183)*	0.793(0.193)***	-0.060(0.219)
Married/Common law			-0.173(0.038)***	0.121(0.025)***
Live with parents			-0.030(0.051)	-0.163(0.036)***
Number of Children				
No child			(base)	(base)
One child			0.081(0.050)	-0.046(0.031)
Two children			0.095(0.053)*	0.008(0.036)
Three children			-0.015(0.074)	-0.050(0.055)
Four or more children			0.060(0.102)	-0.415(0.084)***
Log-likelihood	-69303.97		-42249.15	
Number of observations ^a	185,980		116,740	

Note: This table presents the maximum likelihood estimates of the duration model described in Section 3 using male students only. Columns (1) and (2) contain estimates using the PSIS sample, while columns (3) and (4) feature estimates from the PSIS linked to the T1FF sample, which incorporates additional covariates. Standard errors are shown in brackets adjacent to the

point estimates.

^aAs mandated by Statistics Canada, numbers of observations are rounded to the nearest ten.

*** $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.1$.

Source: Author's calculation.

Table C3: Complete Estimation Results (Female)

	PSIS sample only		PSIS linked to T1FF sample	
	(1) Dropout	(2) Graduate	(3) Dropout	(4) Graduate
Time/Year in Program				
γ_{j1} (Year 1)	-3.966(0.076)***		-3.837(0.092)***	
γ_{j2} (Year 2)	-3.743(0.075)***		-3.661(0.091)***	
γ_{j3} (Year 3)	-3.954(0.076)***	-5.112(0.080)***	-3.876(0.093)***	-4.966(0.094)***
γ_{j4} (Year 4)	-4.277(0.078)***	-3.556(0.051)***	-4.213(0.095)***	-3.398(0.064)***
γ_{j5} (Year 5)	-4.203(0.079)***	-2.121(0.042)***	-4.155(0.096)***	-1.999(0.055)***
γ_{j6} (Year 6)	-3.991(0.083)***	-1.273(0.040)***	-3.953(0.101)***	-1.177(0.053)***
γ_{j7} (Year 7)	-3.429(0.085)***	-0.864(0.041)***	-3.411(0.103)***	-0.791(0.054)***
γ_{j8} (Year 8)	-3.398(0.100)***	-0.622(0.045)***	-3.372(0.120)***	-0.594(0.061)***
γ_{j9} (Year 9)	-3.210(0.123)***	-0.556(0.056)***	-3.285(0.150)***	-0.513(0.078)***
γ_{j10} (Year 10)	-3.206(0.179)***	-0.520(0.071)***	-3.251(0.220)***	-0.470(0.115)***
γ_{j11} (Year 11)		-0.587(0.108)***		
Cohort				
2011 cohort	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
2012 cohort	-0.078(0.042)*	-0.024(0.025)	-0.091(0.049)*	-0.047(0.031)
2013 cohort	-0.107(0.043)**	-0.024(0.028)	-0.128(0.051)**	-0.054(0.035)
2014 cohort	-0.063(0.045)	-0.056(0.035)	-0.116(0.053)**	-0.111(0.044)**
2015 cohort	-0.051(0.047)	-0.038(0.041)	-0.107(0.055)**	-0.136(0.055)**
2016 cohort	-0.054(0.050)	-0.060(0.048)	-0.154(0.059)***	-0.141(0.069)**
COVID	0.236(0.048)***	-0.042(0.031)	0.269(0.056)***	-0.011(0.038)
Initial Immigration Status				
International student	0.062(0.033)*	0.107(0.020)***	-0.117(0.047)**	0.087(0.030)***
Permanent resident	0.122(0.045)***	-0.066(0.031)**	0.108(0.049)**	-0.098(0.038)**
Canadian citizen	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
Get PR/citizenship	-0.207(0.074)***	-0.281(0.031)***	-0.116(0.089)	-0.279(0.042)***
Part-time	0.346(0.048)***	-2.343(0.081)***	0.347(0.052)***	-2.378(0.103)***
Change major	-0.060(0.086)	-0.135(0.047)***	-0.118(0.106)	-0.149(0.064)**
Change institution	-0.049(0.093)	-0.803(0.059)***	-0.057(0.115)	-0.770(0.084)***
Field of Study				
Education	0.190(0.051)***	0.147(0.037)***	0.246(0.058)***	0.189(0.046)***
Visual and Performing Arts	0.386(0.072)***	-0.132(0.057)**	0.502(0.086)***	-0.054(0.078)
Humanities	0.478(0.046)***	-0.499(0.038)***	0.525(0.054)***	-0.525(0.050)***
Social and Behavioural Sciences	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
Business and Management	0.151(0.064)**	-0.138(0.048)***	0.204(0.073)***	-0.245(0.065)***
Physical and Life Sciences	0.061(0.044)	0.501(0.024)***	0.085(0.054)	0.536(0.031)***
Mathematics and Computer Sciences	0.322(0.074)***	0.316(0.046)***	0.406(0.091)***	0.371(0.060)***
Agriculture	0.154(0.078)**	0.424(0.044)***	0.232(0.094)**	0.413(0.058)***
Health	0.175(0.048)***	0.448(0.029)***	0.271(0.054)***	0.426(0.036)***

Legal Studies	0.339(0.096)***	-0.318(0.092)***	0.297(0.125)**	-0.219(0.127)*
Architecture	0.452(0.132)***	-0.222(0.123)*	0.544(0.148)***	-0.363(0.173)**
Engineering	0.156(0.054)***	0.505(0.031)***	0.249(0.067)***	0.522(0.040)***
Multidisciplinary Studies	0.437(0.101)***	0.107(0.075)	0.542(0.113)***	0.054(0.095)
Institution				
Saint Mary's University	-0.446(0.452)	1.624(0.199)***	-0.469(0.506)	1.249(0.260)***
University of Guelph	0.145(0.113)	0.822(0.055)***	0.197(0.128)	0.829(0.065)***
University of Calgary	0.652(0.075)***	0.817(0.044)***	0.579(0.089)***	0.916(0.053)***
Lakehead University	0.622(0.214)***	0.734(0.137)***	0.799(0.221)***	0.590(0.172)***
Laurentian University	0.349(0.204)*	0.676(0.140)***	0.300(0.228)	0.724(0.162)***
Brock University	-0.350(0.272)	0.670(0.124)***	-0.170(0.283)	0.520(0.151)***
University of Western Ontario	0.158(0.082)*	0.650(0.042)***	0.252(0.093)***	0.632(0.051)***
McMaster University	0.369(0.090)***	0.648(0.048)***	0.341(0.107)***	0.675(0.059)***
Toronto Metropolitan University	-0.025(0.168)	0.644(0.077)***	0.056(0.186)	0.704(0.094)***
Ontario Tech University	0.018(0.358)	0.583(0.177)***	0.090(0.384)	0.637(0.215)***
University of Northern British Columbia	0.511(0.171)***	0.554(0.106)***	0.607(0.191)***	0.485(0.130)***
Acadia University	0.558(0.339)	0.523(0.339)	0.619(0.362)*	0.299(0.387)
Wilfrid Laurier University	0.181(0.171)	0.519(0.109)***	0.169(0.199)	0.474(0.136)***
University of Lethbridge	0.883(0.241)***	0.507(0.181)***	0.819(0.295)***	0.627(0.224)***
Queen's University	0.092(0.108)	0.500(0.053)***	0.020(0.133)	0.463(0.066)***
University of Moncton	0.222(0.306)	0.498(0.160)***	0.362(0.339)	0.624(0.195)***
University of Windsor	0.002(0.185)	0.493(0.084)***	0.014(0.207)	0.484(0.097)***
University of Alberta	0.334(0.074)***	0.467(0.040)***	0.327(0.088)***	0.451(0.050)***
University of Victoria	0.428(0.106)***	0.461(0.067)***	0.459(0.125)***	0.349(0.085)***
University of Saskatchewan	0.291(0.107)***	0.406(0.058)***	0.275(0.125)**	0.424(0.071)***
Dalhousie University	-0.069(0.162)	0.373(0.074)***	0.072(0.183)	0.480(0.093)***
Carleton University	0.611(0.091)***	0.362(0.066)***	0.681(0.103)***	0.278(0.085)***
University of Waterloo	0.255(0.094)***	0.354(0.052)***	0.388(0.110)***	0.414(0.069)***
Simon Fraser University	0.144(0.102)	0.262(0.057)***	0.115(0.123)	0.307(0.072)***
University of Ottawa	0.166(0.081)**	0.244(0.046)***	0.256(0.092)***	0.184(0.058)***
University of Northern British Columbia	-0.218(0.504)	0.207(0.224)	0.001(0.505)	0.238(0.274)
Other Universities	0.831(0.067)***	0.141(0.046)***	0.899(0.078)***	0.087(0.061)
University of New Brunswick	0.121(0.160)	0.133(0.103)	0.250(0.176)	0.150(0.132)
University of British Columbia	0.064(0.074)	0.126(0.038)***	0.091(0.088)	0.119(0.048)**
York University	0.591(0.070)***	0.086(0.053)	0.585(0.082)***	0.024(0.068)
University of Sherbrooke	1.102(0.068)***	0.027(0.057)	1.214(0.076)***	-0.176(0.078)**
University of Toronto	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
Laval University	0.775(0.065)***	-0.007(0.044)	0.825(0.078)***	0.003(0.058)
McGill University	0.287(0.070)***	-0.018(0.039)	0.288(0.087)***	-0.087(0.052)*
Trent University	-0.047(0.257)	-0.031(0.148)	0.063(0.297)	-0.071(0.190)
University of Montreal	0.599(0.061)***	-0.042(0.039)	0.615(0.073)***	-0.209(0.053)***
Concordia University	0.016(0.103)	-0.114(0.062)*	-0.088(0.134)	-0.174(0.086)**
University of Quebec in Montreal	0.541(0.075)***	-0.672(0.060)***	0.580(0.085)***	-0.985(0.086)***
Age when first enrol				
21	0.289(0.292)	-0.231(0.183)	0.540(0.321)*	-0.306(0.262)
22	-0.187(0.108)*	0.181(0.051)***	-0.265(0.128)**	0.121(0.065)*
23	-0.121(0.076)	0.165(0.037)***	-0.152(0.092)*	0.182(0.047)***
24	-0.155(0.063)**	0.130(0.030)***	-0.198(0.077)***	0.155(0.038)***
25	(base)	(base)	(base)	(base)
26	0.145(0.059)**	-0.063(0.031)**	0.181(0.071)**	-0.074(0.041)*
27	0.156(0.062)**	-0.157(0.034)***	0.184(0.074)**	-0.144(0.044)***
28	0.239(0.064)***	-0.220(0.037)***	0.215(0.079)***	-0.207(0.048)***
29	0.271(0.067)***	-0.316(0.040)***	0.174(0.085)**	-0.284(0.053)***

30	0.281(0.070)***	-0.394(0.044)***	0.285(0.086)***	-0.350(0.058)***
31	0.453(0.071)***	-0.427(0.048)***	0.433(0.086)***	-0.401(0.065)***
32	0.317(0.080)***	-0.388(0.052)***	0.219(0.096)**	-0.322(0.068)***
33	0.464(0.080)***	-0.396(0.057)***	0.430(0.095)***	-0.333(0.075)***
34	0.554(0.082)***	-0.449(0.063)***	0.463(0.098)***	-0.341(0.079)***
35	0.460(0.087)***	-0.389(0.068)***	0.484(0.101)***	-0.244(0.087)***
36	0.571(0.090)***	-0.380(0.070)***	0.555(0.103)***	-0.296(0.089)***
37	0.551(0.095)***	-0.442(0.077)***	0.575(0.108)***	-0.377(0.101)***
38	0.406(0.101)***	-0.450(0.077)***	0.463(0.113)***	-0.255(0.096)***
39	0.490(0.101)***	-0.289(0.079)***	0.417(0.117)***	-0.203(0.097)**
40	0.408(0.111)***	-0.391(0.084)***	0.465(0.123)***	-0.223(0.106)**
41	0.372(0.113)***	-0.210(0.083)**	0.205(0.131)	-0.115(0.099)
42	0.378(0.116)***	-0.326(0.087)***	0.272(0.137)**	-0.211(0.111)*
43	0.476(0.116)***	-0.333(0.090)***	0.467(0.128)***	-0.212(0.107)**
44	0.430(0.122)***	-0.401(0.099)***	0.424(0.134)***	-0.330(0.122)***
45	0.421(0.131)***	-0.393(0.100)***	0.362(0.148)**	-0.341(0.125)***
46	0.676(0.115)***	-0.380(0.106)***	0.653(0.132)***	-0.178(0.128)
47	0.481(0.132)***	-0.418(0.111)***	0.468(0.145)***	-0.313(0.130)**
48	0.534(0.137)***	-0.458(0.115)***	0.569(0.151)***	-0.413(0.142)***
49	0.738(0.126)***	-0.381(0.119)***	0.685(0.140)***	-0.210(0.136)
50	0.604(0.139)***	-0.545(0.129)***	0.430(0.173)**	-0.495(0.158)***
51	0.917(0.129)***	-0.366(0.130)***	0.840(0.145)***	-0.222(0.151)
52	0.793(0.142)***	-0.139(0.132)	0.783(0.156)***	-0.108(0.161)
53	0.758(0.141)***	-0.651(0.138)***	0.798(0.154)***	-0.594(0.175)***
54	0.681(0.160)***	-0.439(0.152)***	0.684(0.175)***	-0.235(0.179)
55	0.477(0.181)***	-0.426(0.162)***	0.358(0.210)*	-0.631(0.225)***
Married/Common law			-0.133(0.035)***	0.173(0.025)***
Live with parents			-0.199(0.054)***	-0.132(0.036)***
Number of Children				
No child			(base)	(base)
One child			0.201(0.044)***	-0.304(0.032)***
Two children			-0.041(0.052)	-0.289(0.037)***
Three children			-0.021(0.079)	-0.388(0.061)***
Four or more children			-0.224(0.151)	-0.339(0.116)***
Log-likelihood	-60423.08			-40291.49
Number of observations ^a	170,400			118,260

Note: This table presents the maximum likelihood estimates of the duration model described in Section 3 using female students only. Columns (1) and (2) contain estimates using the PSIS sample, while columns (3) and (4) feature estimates from the PSIS linked to the T1FF sample, which incorporates additional covariates. Standard errors are shown in brackets adjacent to the point estimates.

^a As mandated by Statistics Canada, numbers of observations are rounded to the nearest ten.

*** $p < 0.01$; ** $p < 0.05$; * $p < 0.1$.

Source: Author's calculation.